

RELIGIOUS TOLERANCE IS A GUARANTEE OF STABILITY

Mukhsimov Davron Tulkunovich

Independent researcher of Bukhara State University

Bukhara, Uzbekistan

Abstract: This article highlights the culture of tolerance in religious sources and its important aspects for the stability of the society.

Key words: religion, tolerance, culture, Sufism, order, patience, contentment, enlightenment, gnosis, humanity, teaching, perfection.

Introduction. Today, it is important to study the rich spiritual heritage of Mowarounnahr Sufis, to translate them, to introduce important aspects for the spiritual life of modern society. It is known from history that sects in their time encouraged people to mutual harmony and unity. Sufism, which embodies the humanistic ideas of Islam, can serve enough to create a stable situation in our country even today with its spiritual and educational importance.

Methods. Today, in Uzbekistan, the sufism heritage of the representatives of Sufism is being studied deeply and deeply. The pious lifestyles of the Saints of the sect, and their views on purity and honesty, are widely promoted. In all periods of human development, religious and Sufi teachings have gained importance as a factor in ensuring interpersonal tolerance. In fact, the ancient religious books - Avesta, Vedas, Bible and Koran - put forward ideas about the formation of a culture of tolerance. In particular, the ideas about “the struggle between good and evil, light and darkness, truth and falsehood in Zoroastrian ethics” are a reference to the importance of tolerance in ensuring the continuity of humanity. All religions have condemned any kind of ignorance and have taught man to protect himself from himself in favor of virtue.

In Buddhism, the glorification of the "idea of human equality, the monarch's rule of the state with justice, patience" draws attention as evidence that interpersonal relations can be continued with tolerance. Or in the Bible of Christians: "Love your enemies, do good to those who hate you." Pray to the one who cursed you. "Pray for those who have hurt you" is a call for tolerance among people [1].

Also, verses such as "There is no compulsion to religion"(Baqara, verse 256) [2], "Do not curse those who worship other than Allah!" [3] (An'am, verse 108), "O you who believe! Argue with the People of the Book only in the most beautiful manner" (Ankabut, verse 46) in the holy book of Muslims, the Qur'an, are a vivid expression of the ideas of human tolerance.

Therefore, in all religions, human dignity is glorified and mutual kindness and compassion are promoted.

Also, the role of tolerance in the development of society and human spiritual maturity is revealed in the works of great scholars of their time such as Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Khoja Ahmad Yassavi, Amir Temur, Mirza Ulug'bek, Alisher Navoi, Abdurauf Fitrat and Mahmudhoja Behbudi [4].

Tolerance (from the Latin *tolerantia* – patience) means an attitude with understanding to the feelings, opinions, behavior, attitudes, and worldview of another person. Synonyms are tolerance, acceptance, and patience. A tolerant person is a person who has spiritual, moral values and qualities. The opposite example of tolerance is: the child's defense of his own interests, constant insistence on his own, the use of force to resolve various children's conflicts.

For example, Beruni's work "India" preached the need for peoples to live as friends and alliances, and condemned the destructive wars. Abu Nasr Farabi's opinion that "A noble city is a group of people who are naturally healthy and prefer to cooperate with each other" on the one hand serves to ensure stability in society, on the other hand, it represents their movement towards the common goal of creating the common welfare of the community [5]. Ahmad Yassavi also said in the work

“Hikmats”: “The Sunnah is good, don't hurt the unbeliever, God hates the hard hearted one” and emphasized not to hurt the irreligious.

In the idea of Mahmudhoja Behbudi, interethnic tolerance in Islam is glorified “It does not govern the beliefs and consciences of their nationalities, this is because the Holy Qur'an frees the conscience of others and Umrah Islam protects non-religious people” [6]. Abdurauf Fitrat states in the pamphlet “Leader of Salvation” that “Religion consists of moral judgments and brings its followers to the happiness of two worlds, the fruit of human life is this happiness of the present age” [7].

This indicates that the most important quality of citizens is not their racial, national, religious prestige, but dedication of their existence to humanity. So, in Movarounnahr, the ideas of tolerance have manifested themselves in one form or another as the core of various teachings.

Discussion. The great Islamic scholars, Sheikh Muhammad Sadiq Muhammad Yusuf, Alauddin Mansur, Muhammad Taqi Osmani, Dr. Muhammad Said Ramazan Buti and Muhammad Sayyid Tantavi emphasized that the balance of the culture of religious and secular tolerance in their political, religious and social management activities is a guarantee of peace and stability in society [8]. “Today, the whole world, especially the Islamic community, is facing the most dangerous threats of the times. Attempts to politicize Islam and radicalize Muslim youth require serious analysis, evaluation and adequate response to such threats. It should be noted with a thousand regrets that some circles in the world are trying to connect Islam with the ideology of terrorism, increasing anti-Islam sentiment. This factor encourages the Islamic world to become more cohesive. Islamic unity can play an important role in easing the tension in the world”.

Results. The most frequent vectors of tolerance research in sociology are: gender tolerance; racial and national tolerance; tolerance towards the disabled; religious tolerance; sexual orientation tolerance; political tolerance; educational tolerance; inter-class tolerance.

This factor invites the Islamic world to become more united. Islamic unity can play an important role in easing world tensions.

Conclusion. Strengthening the religious and worldly knowledge of young people by effectively using the works of Abu Hanifa, one of the founders of Hanafi teachings in Uzbekistan, “Al-Fiqhu-L-akbar”, “Aqaidu-n-Nasafi” by Abu Hafs Nasafi, “Bad'u-L-Amali” by Osman O'shi, nowadays it is necessary to create a spiritual weapon against the ideas of various fanatical currents arising in the conditions of globalization, to have knowledge based on refutation against the views of destructive currents imported from different regions through the Internet. Therefore, it is important to preserve this tradition by using the rich cultural experiences of the great Imam Abu Hanifah and others.

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